

No	Before	After
1	<code>os.path.exists(path)</code>	<code>os.path.isfile(path)</code>
2	<code>len(d.keys())</code>	<code>len(d)</code>
3	<pre>static = [1, 2, 3] for i in range(len(static)): dim = static[i] print(dim)</pre>	<pre>static = [1, 2, 3] for i, dim in enumerate(static): print(dim)</pre>
4	<code>os.path.exists(path)</code>	<code>os.path.isdir(path)</code>
5	<code>keys = sorted(d.keys())</code>	<code>keys = sorted(d)</code>
6	<code>np.array(range(n))</code>	<code>np.arange(n)</code>
7	<code>self.assertIs(x, True)</code>	<code>self.assertTrue(x)</code>
8	<code>isinstance(f, collections.Callable)</code>	<code>callable(f)</code>
9	<code>os.mkdir(path)</code>	<code>os.makedirs(path)</code>
10	<code>np.random.randint(0, n)</code>	<code>np.random.choice(n)</code>
11	<code>np.log(1 + x)</code>	<code>np.log1p(x)</code>

Change graphs of 11 patterns, which were encountered during mining:

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

6.

7.

8.

9.

10.

11.